

Effect of plow pan depth on rice yield

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Variability in lowland rice growth and grain yields among experimental replications and within subplots reduces data quality and often cannot be explained. One easy to measure factor is plow pan depth.

We conducted a field experiment during 1987 dry season (Jan-May) at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center (MRRTC), Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. Soil was a Vertic Tropaquept with pH 5.9, 14 g organic C/kg, and 1.1 g total N/kg. The experimental design was a randomized complete block with 29 treatments and 4 replications.

IR64 rice was transplanted 20 d after seeding at 4 plants/hill, at 20- × 20-cm spacing (TP) or direct wet seeded. Direct seeding (DS) was by dibbling at the same rate and spacing as transplanting: in rows using, a drum seeder at 20-cm spacing, 80 kg seed/ha (RS); or broadcast at 90 kg seed/ha (BS). Half the plots received 87 kg N as urea/ha.

Plow pan depth after final land preparation was determined in all subplots using a metered stick with a 2.4 cm diameter ball-shaped end weighing 5.6 kg. Penetrating force was 4.9 kg/cm².

Relative yield differences among treatment replications ($100 * X_i *$

X_{mean}^{-1}) were compared to absolute plow pan depth (cm). Pooled linear regressions were performed for N fertilization and for planting methods and geometry.

Plow pan depth (10-30 cm) was correlated significantly with relative grain yield ($P < 0.01$). Yield increase was 2.4% per cm plow pan depth in unfertilized plots and 0.50% in N-fertilized plots (Fig. 1). Among planting methods and geometries, BS gave the strongest yield response to plow pan depth (2.81%/cm, $P < 0.01$), followed by RS (1.60%/cm, $P < 0.01$) and DS (0.48%/cm, $P < 0.01$) (Fig. 2). No correlation was observed in TP.

Plow pan depth strongly affected grain yield. The effect was more pronounced with low N availability. Planting method modulated the plow pan effect, presumably through the number of competing tillers per unit field area. BS had 900 tillers/m² at

1. Relative grain yield of fertilized and unfertilized IR64 as affected by plow pan depth. Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, 1987 dry season.

irrigation schedules—daily and 2 d after water infiltration; two transplanting dates—20 Jun and 5 Jul; and two N levels—120 and 160 kg N/ha, in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

Soil was calcareous sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.0, 0.3% organic C, 14 kg available P/ha, and 136 kg available K/ha. Field capacity and 15 bar water storage in 180-cm soil profile were 40 cm and 14 cm, respectively.

2. Relative grain yield of transplanted, dibbled, row seeded, and broadcast seeded IR64 as affected by plow pan depth. Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, 1987 dry season.

maturity and showed the strongest response to plow pan depth; TP (500 tillers/m²) showed no response. RS and DS had intermediate tiller numbers and response to plow pan depth. The response of yield to plow pan depth (YR) depended significantly on tiller number (TN), following the equation:

$$\text{YR} (\% \text{ increase/cm depth}) = -3.25 + 0.00677 \text{ TN} (\text{tillers/m}^2) r 0.991^{**}$$

We conclude that in lowland ricefield experiments, plow pan depth is an important influence on growth and yield of rice and should be kept constant through appropriate land preparation or be monitored to explain variability of data and to interpret experimental results more adequately. □

Effect of the interaction of transplanting date, irrigation schedule, and nitrogen on rice yield

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We studied the interaction of irrigation schedule and N on PR106 rice transplanted on different dates in 1982 and 1983. Treatments were two

Shallow submergence was maintained in all plots for 3 wk after transplanting. Irrigation treatments were continued to 1 wk before harvest. At transplanting, 1/3 N, 13 kg P, and 24 kg K/ha were broadcast and mixed into the topsoil. The remaining N was topdressed in equal splits 3 and 6 wk after transplanting.

Effective tillers, number of spikelets per panicle, and panicle weight were recorded. Grain yield was expressed at 15% moisture content.